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Research In Progress

Exploring Co-Agency in Human-Machine Assemblages: Toward a Methodology for Collective Intelligence Design

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Abstract

The rise of new forms of human-machine collaboration raises questions for living lab methodologies that aim to comprehend machines as elements in complex dynamic systems rather than distinct technological objects. We argue that it makes sense to approach infrastructures integrating human and machinic agency as stacks, building on an existing systems design discourse that already adopts a holistic view of the integration of soft- and hardware as well as dynamic contexts. The goal of this paper is to make the case that such an approach facilitates the creation of new living lab methodologies and encourages actors to reexamine the common sense informing our concepts of human and machinic agency.

Keywords

co-creation methodologies, coagency, stack, collective intelligence design, human-computer interaction, cognitive assemblages, value

Exploring Co-Agency in Human-Machine Assemblages:

Toward a Methodology for Collective Intelligence Design

"We need not one but many stack design theories." Benjamin Bratton

The rise of new forms of human-machine collaboration raises questions for living lab methodologies that aim to comprehend machines as elements in complex dynamic systems rather than distinct technological objects. We argue that it makes sense to approach infrastructures integrating human and machinic agency as stacks, building on an existing systems design discourse that already adopts a holistic view of the integration of soft- and hardware as well as dynamic contexts. The goal of this paper is to make the case that such an approach facilitates the creation of new living lab methodologies and encourages actors to reexamine the common sense informing our concepts of human and machinic agency.

1. The space of action is changing. Or: Engaging with the emergence of co-agency

Much of the work across our living lab communities revolves around action: living labs are "do tanks", they focus on practices of collaboration and co-creation, and when it comes to policy initiatives, a key concern is action-orientation. Because of the centrality of action to these approaches, changes in the way we comprehend agency are highly relevant to what we do - as individual actors in a local living lab community, as researchers engaged in transfer activities, as policy makers committed to seeing real change in the world, as citizens interested in the democratic design of digital societies.

We argue that in the emergent age of intelligent machines, the time has come to re-engage with the question of agency. A term we more or less have come to take for granted, our individual and collective agency is undergoing a transformation we are only beginning to understand. But it already seems apparent that the more we rely on intelligent machines in the organization of how we communicate, relate and create, the more enmeshed human and machine agency will become - to the extent that we feel it necessary to no longer think of them as separate but as a hybrid form of agency. We use the term "co-agency" to emphasize this interest in the exploration, comprehension, and design of these forms of agency.

"We describe as co-agency the combination of human and machinic agency in new socio-technological assemblages."

We know, of course, that all agency is relational - we become who we are, how we think and act, through others, through the web of relations we weave around us over the course of our lives. Whenever we act, these others, through the traces these relations have left, are implicated ("folded into") and involved ("wrapped up") in what we do.

Increasingly, machines are part of how this web of relations is woven. Our interest in the regulation of the major players in the platform economy, for instance, does not only arise from concerns regarding market monopolies. To the extent that we allow these platforms to become part of a wide array of our daily gestures, how these platforms operate - the rules of engagement they define through their end user licences, the way they organize our workflows through their user experience design strategies, the incentives they offer to encourage us to participate in the data mining and value creation processes on which their business models are based - affects how we do things. That is to say, they affect who we are and become as we rely more and more on these platforms as *de facto* enabling environments for whatever it is we do.¹

Yet although we act through them, we have very little say in how these logics of operation are defined. Our devices tell us when updates are in order, and once installed, we are confronted with new interfaces. So we adapt, we go with the flow, especially since security concerns have come to convince us that such updates are crucial to our own safety in these online environments. And even if we were to hesitate to play by these rules - there is very little we can do. Other than a collective exodus into the worlds of free software and federated infrastructures, an option we will return to later, in part because it has come to inform official European policy on the role of “technological sovereignty” in the future of innovation, in part because such an exodus has turned out to be quite difficult to organize as its preconditions - data portability, for example - do not yet exist.

We think that rather than framing our exploration of emerging technologies in the dichotomous terms of analogue and digital, we think that we need to take seriously the possibility that we must approach these concerns from *within* our relation with machines. More than a term of analysis, the concept of co-agency offers us a perspective, a point of view from which to explore our situation from within this relation. And if in fact we act through these relational infrastructures, a first step in the exploration of the role they play is to find a way to comprehend them. One way of doing that is to enter the stack.

2. Enter the stack

While the power of platforms arises from network effects - people will move to whatever platform promises to best amplify their agency -, we think there is more to

¹ Also see the ILO toolkit on “enabling environments” <www.ilo.org/eese>, an approach that does not yet take this co-agency into account. Interested in a more nuanced sense of “environment”, we agree that “[w]e need a bridging motion from congenial humanistic assumptions to difficult explorations of a bewildering array of sciences including evolutionary biology, biochemistry, neuroscience, biophysics, geomorphology, ecology and ethology” (Wendy Wheeler and Louise Westling, “Biosemiotics and culture: introduction”, *Green Letters*, 19:3 (2015), 215-226, DOI: 10.1080/14688417.2015.1078973); here, we can only gesture toward such a motion.

the story, and we need to look beyond user numbers and market share.² Instead, we should look at how these platforms exercise their power at the level of infrastructure. Every major platform exercises its power to create markets through a mix of software and hardware standards that effectively structure the kind of agency available in the platform ecosystem. We call this mix “the stack”.

For software developers, a stack is a data structure that serves as a collection of elements with two main operations (addition / removal of elements - a “stack overflow error” indicates that no more elements can be added, for instance). For systems designers, a stack can also be a conceptual systems model to characterise and standardise the functions of a communication system. For critical observers of the platform economy like the cultural theorist Benjamin Bratton, the stack is an “accidental megastructure” that also includes the material contexts that allow such a system to operate (example: in the case of mobile communications, such contexts range from mineral mining to satellite networks).³ We use it here in a broader sense: the stack is everything that affects - directly or indirectly - the kind of agency available in a given context.

“We describe as the stack the infrastructural principle of operation of a complex dynamic system.”

What the stack does is put a set of values in action. We mean this quite literally - the stack is the engine of the value creation models that inform the system in question (example: a principle of limited interoperability restricts potential uses of the data processed by the system - while we are used to taking our mobile number and contacts from one provider to another, you cannot simply move your chat messages and contacts from one messenger to the next as these two practices are subject to different regulations).

In the early 21st century, we effectively live in the stack. The “accidental megastructures” (Bratton) of the multiple technological infrastructures and data-driven platforms - the stacks - sustaining our ways of life effectively structure how we relate to ourselves, to each other, and to the world around us. One of the major obstacle to innovation in Europe is that we cannot anticipate a radical redesign of these stacks. A current initiative that is highly relevant to the living lab community and its growing interest in facilitating the creation of data-driven business models is the start of “GAIA-X”, a network to create a federated data infrastructure based on the values of transparency, openness, data protection and security.⁴ Part of this effort is

² Ben Evans, “Would breaking up 'big tech' work? What would?” (2020 / 08 / 10), <<https://www.ben-evans.com/benedictevans/2020/8/10/would-breaking-up-big-tech-work>>

³ Benjamin H. Bratton, *The Stack: On Software and Sovereignty*, MIT Press, 2014.

⁴ <https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/>

the creation of a “sovereign cloud stack”.⁵ Its inventors claim that “[w]hat we need today is not just a fresh awareness of data sovereignty, but the IT infrastructure to go along with it, too. We need a whole new open-source infrastructure”.⁶ So for us, “the stack” is where the rubber of policy (“data sovereignty”) hits the road of structural transformation (“sovereign stack”) to create different innovation ecosystems.

By definition, a new stack lays the foundation of new future and emerging technologies. Influential open tech stack models include the OSI and TCP/IP stack, the most influential (market-creating) stacks are those of major platform providers (Airbnb, Amazon, Facebook, Slack, Uber). To address the dominance of these players requires challenging the dominance of these underlying technology stacks.⁷ We argue that because at the heart of each innovation ecosystem is a technology stack, we need new stacks for a new ecosystem to emerge.

“We invite living lab communities to imagine and co-create a new stack for collective intelligence design as an enabling environment to encourage and amplify emerging forms of human-machine collaboration.”

We are convinced that it is no longer sufficient to address state, market, and civil society when we engage in worldmaking - we must urgently imagine, address, and design the stack as a separate layer of our collective existence. However, when we, Europe’s citizens, currently look at (technological) innovation, many of us feel like mice in a maze: while the ways in which everyday lives are structured is changing radically, there is no single perspective from which these changes could be comprehended, or whether there is even a way out of the labyrinth. Empowering users to engage in anticipatory technology assessment, we must urgently find ways to comprehend and co-design stacks as assemblages of distributed systems anticipate future forms of co-agency enabled by alternative stacks , and thereby create the conditions for future innovation by creating **a collective intelligence design stack**.

As holistic views of (viable) systems design gain ground, the question of how we might turn the “accidental megastructure” of existing infrastructure stacks into consciously designed collective intelligence architectures has emerged as a key challenge for Europe’s digital societies.⁸ Our main objective is to inspire the development and

⁵ <http://scs.community/>

⁶ <https://www.sprind.org/en/projects/sovereign-cloud-stack/>

⁷ One of the most influential network architecture stacks is the seven-layer reference model for Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) developed by the International Organization for Standards and the International Electrotechnical Commission, see <<https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso-iec:7498:-1:ed-1:v2:en>>.

⁸ Geoff Mulgan, *Big Mind: How Collective Intelligence Can Change Our World*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2017.

prototypical implementation of a collective intelligence design stack - a radical break with existing approaches to the design of technological systems to foreground the capacity of systems to amplify our capacity to act as part of collective intelligences. Adopting the principle that such technology stacks are in principle subject to co-design, we invite living lab communities to embark on a series of complementary co-design processes to explore how we might best facilitate the emergence of new forms of co-agency to enable such co-design.

The power of innovation lies not in its appearance but its widespread adoption. The prerequisite for such adoption is that **the new changes the way we relate to ourselves, to each other, and to the world**. The mobile phone still serves as a core example, as it laid the foundation for the redesign of numerous infrastructures, networks, and value chains. But the mobile phone alone is not the technological innovation - **what is new is the technology stack** of which it is a part and which allows it to create such powerful disruptive effects. And the initial innovation was not a technical object, but the **imagination of a world** in which communication would be radically decentralized and cut across the boundaries between creation, distribution, and use. We therefore contend that we must open imaginaries to future world-making.⁹ Moving beyond the popular-yet-problematic “design thinking” schema, **we invite you to co-create the story and a playbook for such worldmaking**.

3. Revisiting Co-Agency: Ethics, Trust, Cooperation

As actors in living lab communities and networks, should this interest us to the extent that we learn to “think infrastructure”? Are we calling on all of us to become stack designers? Yes and no - it is more complex than a binary decision, as one would imagine when it comes to agency in complex adaptive systems.¹⁰ So let us return to the foundations of what we do, as suggested earlier in our exploration of co-agency.

We have been told that the literacies needed in a democratic society - the literacies that ensure we can actually exercise and enjoy the individual and collective agency to which we are constitutionally entitled in many, if not all of the societies covered by the living lab network - will have to be broadened to address the changes these societies are undergoing in the wake of technological transformation, including calls for the

⁹ Mark Graham, Rob Kitchin, Shannon Mattern, Joe Shaw, Joe, eds., *How to Run a City Like Amazon, and Other Fables*. London: Meatspace Press, 2019.

¹⁰ We find the term “human-machine interaction” misleading as it seems to focus on the relationship between one human and one machinic actor, whereas we see a need to engage with cognitive assemblages: “A cognitive assemblage emphasizes the flow of information through a system and the choices and decisions that create, modify, and interpret the flow. While a cognitive assemblage may include material agents and forces (and almost always does so), it is the cognizers within the assemblage that enlist these affordances and direct their powers to act in complex situations”, N. Katherine Hayles, *Unthought: The Power of the Cognitive Nonconscious*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2017, 169.

“citizen coder” (a term that arose about a decade ago, it now resonates with related ideas such as “citizen science”). While we emphatically embrace this idea (coding teaches logic, after all), we also want to suggest that we need something like an “infrastructural literacy” that extend such literacies to the systems. The suggestion to think “co-agency” is part of such an effort. This is not as new as it seems. Citizens have long been engaging with technological transformation on multiple levels, the current exploration of mobile network strategies (witness the skepticism regarding the deployment of 5G technologies) can be reconnected to a long history of critical technology assessments. These have already been developed into pragmatic “Constructive Technology Assessments, and we make the case that these methods can and should be developed even further to allow **“anticipatory technology assessment”**”.¹¹

Ethics is the field where we currently attempt to imagine how these developments might best be governed, with limited success - unease regarding the proposed integration of “ecosystems of excellence” and “ecosystems of trust” is palpable on every page of the EU’s recent policy documents.¹² And yet we seem to miss something fundamental: we need to safeguard not only our individual human agency but our ability to **co-exist in a new generation of collective intelligences** that radically alter our understanding of the ways in which humans and machines collaborate. When pioneers of ubiquitous computing such as Mark Weiser refer to the key role of implicit knowledges, they point us to the limits of “making things public” and in fact of openness as master paradigm, stressing the **need for new types of co-agency interfaces to mobilize such knowledges**.¹³ We can draw on these historical anticipations of a tech stack that would be so comprehensive as to become invisible to create the prototype of such an interface. Today, we urgently need to revisit such optimism regarding the symbiosis of human and machinic agency to **better anticipate the consequences of the radical redesign of human agency**

¹¹ Johan Schot and Arie Rip, “The Past and Future of Constructive Technology Assessment”, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 54 (1997), pp. 251-66; Roberto Poli and Marco Valerio, Marco, eds., *Anticipation, Agency and Complexity*, Heidelberg: Springer, 2019. We have been discussing such efforts in the context of the anticipate network, a multidisciplinary research effort to integrate anticipation approaches from the arts, technology studies, and the social sciences and humanities to create anticipatory scenarios involving a wide array of stakeholders in foresighting activities <<https://www.anticipate.network/>>.

¹² EC, “On Artificial Intelligence -A European approach to excellence and trust”, White Paper. Brussels: EC, 2020, <https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/commission-white-paper-artificial-intelligence-feb2020_en.pdf>

¹³ Mark Weiser, “The Computer for the 21st Century”, *Scientific American* (September 1991); also see Adam Greenfield, *Radical technologies: the design of everyday life*. New York, NY: Verso Books, 2017.

Europe’s digital societies have effectively engaged in through their comprehensive digital agendas.¹⁴

The dominant approach to “black box” technologies whose “internal” workings are difficult to comprehend and govern is to “open” these boxes - the vocabulary of openness, transparency, and visibility informs our approaches to accountability and in fact our narratives of democratic governance. We suggest approaching the stack as an assemblage that cannot be “opened” in its entirety - not because of ill-will or lack of resolve, but because the stack is not a technological object or dynamic that can be observed from any single vantage point.

Once we adopt “co-agency” as analytical perspective, we can develop this further since what we need are distributed points of view to explore distributed systems. Which is why we make the case to shift our focus from agency to co-agency to better comprehend the extent to which human and machinic agency already affect one another. We wish to start another, more complex innovation narrative - through activities across the living lab network that make tangible how we might come to terms and take advantage of the contexts of distributed socio-technological systems for future innovation.

We also contend that only ambitious visions create space for breakthrough innovation. The vision of a collective intelligence design stack is such a vision - we know that the development of a complete stack is an incredibly ambitious goal and is likely to involve much more than a single technology research project. At the same time, we believe that this vision **opens up a new kind of technology design conversation** that can actually address and engage with the radicality of the current change in human-machine relations.

The realization that “humans are no longer the only symbolic cognizers on the planet, and indeed not necessarily the most powerful” (N. Katherine Hayles) is seen by many European citizens not as an opportunity but a humiliation, calling into question the central role of the human in our views of the future. We see something else - a notion of freedom that arises from the acknowledgment of the necessarily limited scope of human agency, and an optimistic view of a new relationalism that focuses on the role (natural and machinic) environments play in new forms of co-agency. Resolutely committing itself to a perspective that places human and non-human actors on the same playing field to anticipate future forms of co-agency, we therefore embrace both the sense of opportunity and a humble view of human agency.

Our argument is inspired by a vision of the technology stacks structuring and sustaining our agency as harboring the potential for enormous mutual empowerment. Given that the rapid pace of technological transformation is met with a complex nexus

¹⁴ Riel Miller, Riel, ed., *Transforming the future: anticipation in the 21st century*, Paris. UNESCO, 2019.

of negative effects across Europe (anxiety, exhaustion, fear, insecurity, disengagement from political processes), such optimism carries significant risks because it may be considered to entrench rather than exit from the technology-centrism of Europe's innovation agenda. But the collaboration strategies we hope to develop are meant to inspire trust in such a co-creation process - knowing that the lack of trust in such complex systems design processes (and in the ability of policymakers effectively to govern them) are among the biggest obstacles to innovation.

4. New Approaches to Co-Creation and Innovation Governance

To set up a co-creation framework, we propose the following three research vectors to facilitate the definition of new living lab methodologies for such an effort:

4.1. Investigate Collective Intelligence Design as Key Enabling Technology to safeguard not only our individual human agency but our ability to co-exist in a new generation of collective intelligences that radically alter our understanding of the ways in which humans and machines collaborate.

4.2. Explore Emerging Forms of Human-Machine Interaction to fundamentally re-evaluate our ideas of human-machine interaction. Rather than assuming that the primary relationship to be comprehended and designed is that between an individual user and their machine, we shift the focus to new collective intelligences - the vast human-machine assemblages powered by artificial, augmented, and distributed intelligences - to anticipate new forms of co-agency they make possible.

4.3. Provide a Prototypical Implementation of the Collective Intelligence Design Stack. Using (for instance) the seven-layer OSI model for stack development as a general reference dynamic, we can design a stack prototype and make it available as an open stack to facilitate widespread adoption and reuse across living lab communities.

If Europe is aiming at "technological sovereignty", future ecosystems for products and services must be based on alternative technology stacks.¹⁵ Additionally, such alternative stacks must be capable of sustaining an expanding spectrum of value-creating activities - the sharing economy and the return of "public value" are evidence of a broader transformation of value and the markets designed to facilitate the generation and distribution of such value.¹⁶

¹⁵ <https://ecipe.org/publications/europes-technology-sovereignty/>

¹⁶ Mariana Mazzucato, "Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union: A problem-solving approach to fuel innovation-led growth", Brussels: EC DG Research and Innovation, 2018, <https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/mazzucato_report_2018.pdf>

These developments are also indicative of a fundamental shift in how we comprehend, approach, and ultimately govern innovation - we know now that even technological innovation is never simply “technological” but depends on a wide array of other (cultural, political, social) innovations. If Europe intends to benefit from the emergence of new forms of (public) value, it must embrace a more holistic view of how such value is generated.¹⁷ We invite living lab communities to make an important initial contribution to such an alternative innovation infrastructure by focusing on a collective intelligence design stack and find ways to effectively combine technological and non-technological innovation.

As of today, high-level research on collective intelligence design (CID) is centered outside of Europe and the EIT has yet to initiate major innovation dynamics to engage with this emerging research field. And while the field of CID has matured across Europe, it lacks an integrative dynamic to expand and scale such efforts.¹⁸ We contend that defining and prototyping a CID stack will give these developments a substantial push and serve as a common technological core of future innovation efforts. Hoping to mobilize interest from across living lab communities, we aim to contribute through such a collaborative effort to the creation of robust technology assessment frameworks, design guidelines, and criteria for assessment and certification. This will allow us to critically **address the limits of conventional innovation narratives**, whose narrow “plots” are reinforced by the logic of venture capital looking for “singular” and “disruptive” rather than systems-based forms of innovation, even though only the latter build innovation ecosystems.

5. Outlook: Exploring the Future of Value

The aim of all innovation is the creation of value. We believe that innovation methods must prioritize the comprehension of value to best assist users in future value-creating activities. The distribution of technological systems - the stack - radically changes how value is created and the meaning of value itself. If we think innovation beyond technology-based products and services to engage with the full spectrum of cultural, economic, and social innovation, it becomes clear that **value is not only realized through markets but across a wide field of human activity.**¹⁹

¹⁷ Caroline Criado Perez, *Invisible Women*, London: Chatto & Windus, 2019.

¹⁸ One indicator of the growing interest in the field is the recent launch of a research journal dedicated to collective intelligence <https://www.nesta.org.uk/press-release/sage-and-association-computing-machinery-announce-new-open-access-journal-field-collective-intelligence-collaboration-nesta/>

¹⁹ Brian Massumi, *99 Theses on the Revaluation of Value*, Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2018

The digital transformation has already made every EU citizen aware that digital objects can be both used and shared, upsetting traditional value chains across all of Europe's industries. These shareable assets may be temporarily protected by IP, but the exclusiveness of use assumed by IP is part of a limited innovation narrative that cannot address the **co-existence of multiple, overlapping, and incommensurable values**. The return of "public" value as a concern is a symptom of the exhaustion of this well-established view of innovation, as is the emergence of **new economies where users are both consumers and creators**. In its focus on a new stack, we wish to bring future innovation actors into play whose capacity for co-creation we have not even begun to explore - but cannot afford to ignore.

